

FORMATION OF SOLVATES IN SULPHUR MONOCHLORIDE

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Formation of solvates from several anhydrous compounds in sulphur monochloride has been investigated.

Spong (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 485) put forward the view that sulphur monochloride was probably a mixture of two isomeric forms, having the structures (I) and (II).

This has been supported by Giacomello (*Atti R. Accad. Lincei*, 1935, 21, 36), Lengfeld (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 449), Meuwesen (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 121) and Stamm (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 673).

Electron diffraction studies (Palmer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2360) have shown that in the vapour phase sulphur monochloride has structures (III) or (IV).

Syrkin and Dyatkina ("Structure of Molecules", Butterworth Scientific Publications, 1950) on the basis of calculations of bond energies have shown that there is a possibility of the existence of ionic structures (V) and (VI) in addition to the homopolar structures (III) and (IV).

If these ionic structures exist in sulphur monochloride, it is natural to expect that it will show some of the properties common to polar solvents. In the present work formation of solvates in sulphur monochloride has been studied.

Sulphur monochloride on coming in contact with anhydrous aluminium chloride reacts exothermally, forming a compound $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$, which is only slightly soluble in it and separates out as a thick red liquid, heavier than sulphur monochloride. This solvate was prepared by Ruff and Golla (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1924, 138, 17). On heating it strongly they obtained $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$. It has, however, been

observed that on controlled heating at 135-40°, the disolvate $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$ loses a molecule of sulphur monochloride and changes to a monosolvate, $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$, according to

It is a red crystalline solid and with more sulphur monochloride changes back to disolvate.

Anhydrous ferric chloride has also been found to form a disolvate, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$, a dark pungent solid which is quite stable up to 200°. In earlier attempts to prepare a compound of sulphur monochloride with ferric chloride, Ezdakov (*Chem. Abs.*, 1942, 36, 5439²) bubbled chlorine through the reaction mixture. The compound, thus obtained, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$, is in fact a compound derived from the unstable SCl_4 rather than from sulphur monochloride. In Table I is shown a list of solvates prepared from different anhydrous compounds.

Arsenic trichloride and stannic chloride have been found to be freely miscible with sulphur monochloride, while phosphoryl chloride, which is also freely miscible with sulphur monochloride, forms a compound containing sulphur (composition not definite).

Apart from these inorganic compounds, some organic bases as pyridine and α -picoline also have been found to afford the solvates, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot 2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$. These solvates have a low solubility in sulphur monochloride and crystallise out on cooling.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sulphur monochloride used in the present work was redistilled over elementary sulphur to remove any sulphur dichloride which might be present there. Other chemicals used for the preparation of solvates were dehydrated according to the methods (a to e) given in the literature :

- (a) AlCl_3 and FeCl_3 were sublimed in a slow current of Cl_2 .
- (b) CuSO_4 , CuO and BiOCl heated to constant weights.
- (c) CuCl_2 heated in a current of Cl_2 gas.
- (d) CoCl_2 , ZnCl_2 , MnCl_2 , CaCl_2 , BaCl_2 , CdCl_2 and SrCl_2 were dehydrated by heating in a current of dry HCl gas.
- (e) Pyridine and α -picoline distilled over solid KOH .

To prepare the solvates, the solute (about 5 g.) was slowly added to sulphur monochloride (100 c.c.) in a 250 c.c. standard-joint pyrex flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a CaCl_2 -tube to avoid all contact with moist air. The flask, if required, was cooled during the process of addition. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours and then cooled. The solid separating out was filtered in dry atmosphere and kept in vacuo to remove the excess of adhering sulphur monochloride.

All these manipulations and transfers were done in a dry box. The compounds were analysed according to the standard methods and the results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Substance taken.	Solvate formed.	Calc.	Found.	State of the substance formed.
AlCl ₃ (5 g.)	AlCl ₃ .2S ₂ Cl ₂ (14 g.)	Al: 6.60% Cl: 67.00	6.70% 60.23	Red liquid.
	AlCl ₃ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (9 g.) (m.p. 168°)	Al: 10.00 Cl: 66.00	10.00 65.50	Red crystalline solid.
FeCl ₃ (5 g.)	FeCl ₃ .2S ₂ Cl ₂ (11 g.)	Fe: 12.95 Cl: 57.40	12.80 56.76	Dark solid.
CuCl ₂ (5 g.)	CuCl ₂ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (5 g.)	Cu: 23.56 Cl: 52.69	23.66 52.22	Brick-red solid.
CoCl ₂ (5 g.)	CoCl ₂ .2S ₂ Cl ₂ (12 g.)	Co: 14.70 Cl: 53.20	14.70 52.40	Pink solid.
ZnCl ₂ (5 g.)	ZnCl ₂ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (8.5 g.)	Zn: 23.50 Cl: 52.40	24.00 51.60	Yellowish white solid.
MnCl ₂ (5 g.)	MnCl ₂ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (9 g.)	Mn: 21.80 Cl: 54.40	20.90 54.10	Buff-coloured solid.
CaCl ₂ (4 g.)	CaCl ₂ .8S ₂ Cl ₂ (24 g.)	Ca: 3.36 Cl: 53.65	3.39 54.10	White crystalline solid.
BaCl ₂ (5 g.)	BaCl ₂ .4S ₂ Cl ₂ (19 g.)	Ba: 18.30 Cl: 47.40	18.60 46.80	Light buff-coloured solid.
CdCl ₂ (5 g.)	CdCl ₂ .2S ₂ Cl ₂ (9.5 g.)	Cd: 24.70 Cl: 47.90	24.50 47.10	Greyish white solid.
SrCl ₂ (6 g.)	SrCl ₂ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (8 g.)	Sr: 29.80 Cl: 48.30	29.50 47.90	Yellowish white solid.
CuSO ₄ (5 g.)	2CuSO ₄ .S ₂ Cl ₂ (7 g.) (CuSO ₄ .½S ₂ Cl ₂)	Cu: 27.90 Cl: 15.60	28.00 15.40	White crystalline solid.
CuO (5 g.)	CuO.S ₂ Cl ₂ (12 g.)	Cu: 29.60 Cl: 33.10	30.10 33.26	Dark solid.
BiOCl (5 g.)	BiOCl.S ₂ Cl ₂ (6.5 g.)	Bi: 52.80 Cl: 26.99	52.20 26.50	Yellowish white solid.
Pyridine (5 g.)	C ₅ H ₅ N.S ₂ Cl ₂ (12 g.)	S: 29.99 Cl: 33.17	30.00 33.72	Reddish yellow crystalline solid.
α-Picoline (4 g.)	C ₈ H ₇ N.2S ₂ Cl ₂ (13 g.)	S: 35.26 Cl: 39.19	34.99 39.23	Dark liquid.

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